

IMI2 Project 802750 - FAIRplus
FAIRification of IMI and EFPIA data

WP3 - Identification of and implementation of data on sustainable data hosting platforms

D3.5 Provide IMI FAIR Data Catalogue

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1. Executive Summary

The IMI FAIR Data Catalog is being developed as a single point of entry to the diverse range of projects and datasets available in the Innovative Medicine Initiative (IMI), Horizon 2020 (H2020) and other biomedical research initiatives funded by the European Commission. It is built on a flexible community standard, the Data Tag Suite (DATS) data model, which is able to accommodate a wide range of biomedical data types as well as being interoperable with other standards such as DCAT and Bioschemas. The current round of work included improvements on all aspects of FAIR, improving the user experience and expanding the Catalog content through active curation efforts.

2. Background

The predecessor of the IMI FAIR Data Catalog was developed in a partnership between the IMI-eTriks project¹ and ELIXIR-Luxembourg as a kind of 'one-stop shop' to show the datasets that are available in IMI, H2020 projects and other projects, as well as published sources, allowing partners to promote their solutions and encourage data sharing. The aim was to create value for public and private organisations and translational researchers and drive research collaboration formation towards convergence and precision medicine.

In the FAIRplus project, we expanded the data model of the Data Catalog to adopt community accepted data models and accommodate more use cases and data types. Alongside these developments, the Data Catalog infrastructure was developed further and populated gradually with more and more projects. The main goal of the Data Catalog is to support the Findability and Reuse of datasets generated in projects funded by the IMI Joint Undertaking.

3. Results

3.1. Data model

The initial Data Catalog data model was heavily skewed towards translational medicine and classic human clinical trial datasets, focusing on cohort and patient characteristics, treatment and interventions. This model makes it difficult, however, to include thematically related study types such as pharmacological, toxicological or drug repurposing studies in animals or in vitro systems. At the same time, the FAIR principles encourage the adoption of recognised community standards wherever possible in order to facilitate data sharing and reuse.

For this reason, we decided to adopt and adapt the Data Tag Suite (DATS)² data model for use in the Data Catalog. DATS is a data description model designed and produced to describe datasets being ingested in DataMed³, a prototype for data discovery developed as part of the bioCADDIE project⁴. DATS was co-developed by the Oxford e-Research Centre, which is also a partner on the FAIRplus project and the NIH Data Common Big Data to Knowledge (BD2K)

¹ <https://www.etriks.org/>

² <https://github.com/datatagsuite/README>

³ <https://datamed.org/>

⁴ <https://dbmi.ucsd.edu/projects/biocaddie.html>

initiative⁵, where it was used to uniformly represent metadata across a number of projects, including the Genotype-Tissue Expression project (GTEx)⁶ and Trans-Omics for Precision Medicine (TOPMed)⁷. DATS is semantically compatible with the Data Catalog Vocabulary (DCAT)⁸, a Resource Description Framework (RDF)⁹ vocabulary designed to facilitate interoperability among data catalogs published on the web, as well as schema.org (SDO)¹⁰, which is a community-driven effort with a similar interoperability goal to DCAT but a more general-purpose scope.

The original DATS model is centred around the generic core concept of a “DataSet”, an entity that covers technical aspects such as licensing, data types and distributions. The DataSet is produced by or is the input or output of a “Study”, which contains elements that are specific for life, environmental and biomedical science domains, and which models experimental processes, cohort and protocol information. We extended the DATS model further to include the third core concept of “Project”, covering general information such as title, publications, funding and contributors. This effectively created the concept triangle shown in fig. 1.

Figure 1. The Data Catalog Data Model

In Data Catalog DATS, “Project” is the core part of any entry. Every study and dataset is expected to belong to a project. Each project can contain any number of studies, which in turn can be linked to any number of datasets. Datasets can also be linked directly to a project if no study-related information is available.

This structure is not dissimilar to the ISA (Investigation, Study, Assay) model¹¹ but increases

⁵ <https://commonfund.nih.gov/bd2k>

⁶ <https://www.gtexportal.org/home/>

⁷ <https://www.nhlbi.nih.gov/science/trans-omics-precision-medicine-topmed-program>

⁸ <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-2/>

⁹ <https://www.w3.org/RDF/>

¹⁰ <https://schema.org/>

¹¹ <https://isa-specs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/index.html>

flexibility as datasets can exist independently of studies, whereas ISA assays require the presence of a study in a data object. Another key difference between the two models is their ultimate focus: while ISA is designed to present metadata about the experimental process, the measurements and tests involved, DATS focuses on different aspects of datasets, such as their availability, access restrictions and technical details. Metadata on experimental procedures are included to aid findability and interoperability, rather than in order to represent the full scope of the experiment.

Each of the core data objects in DATS contains a set of sub-objects, which in turn contain further sub-objects, down to the lowest unitary object (which contains no further objects), which is the “Annotation”. An “Annotation” consists of just two key-value pairs, the “value” and, optionally, the “valueIRI”, designed to capture the Internationalized Resource Identifier (IRI)¹² of an ontology term contextualising the free text “value”. Due to this nested object structure, DATS can be quite opaque to parse for the human reader but allows for easier programmatic processing of the objects. A full overview of the DATS schema can be found on the [DataTagSuite Github repository](#).

In order to remain lightweight and flexible, the original DATS model includes very few core properties (see Table 1). Instead, it provides the option to add additional information for any entity via ad-hoc key-value pairs. During the review of the existing content of the Data Catalog, we identified a number of commonly recurring properties, such as “phone number” for project contributors and “project website” for projects, which we decided to include in the model as permanent properties.

Table 1. Core properties of the IMI Data Catalog Data Model

Data object	Core properties	Recommended properties
PROJECT	title, types, projectLeads	description, acronym, start/end date, funding, projectWebsite
STUDY	name	description, studyGroups, characteristics
DATASET	title, types, creators	description, creation date, version, dataStandard, types, dimensions, isAbout, licenses

While we aim to keep the adapted DATS model relatively stable in order to maximise compatibility with other resources, we also regularly review incoming information regarding new data types to identify recurring information that would benefit from formal integration into the model, including semantic definition via JSON-LD¹³ context.

3.2. Development

Web interface

We redeveloped the Data Catalog user portal web application with extended search facilities as well as a more appealing and intuitive user interface, improving user experience. The three

¹² <https://www.w3.org/International/O-URL-and-ident.html>

¹³ <https://json-ld.org/>

concepts from the core model are presented as separate facets in the user interface, allowing the user to choose which aspect they are most interested in. Concepts are, however, also fully interlinked to allow users to easily move between them.

As part of the redevelopment, we reviewed the properties displayed in the original Data Catalog and adapted these to allow the inclusion of a more diverse range of studies and datasets.

The Data Catalog stores and indexes the metadata using Solr¹⁴. The backend is a Python application using Flask¹⁵ as a web framework. The user interface is developed using HTML, CSS and jQuery¹⁶. A few facets are pre-defined (data types, disease, keywords, samples types) to provide rapid filters and it is possible to change the defaults or add more by configuration. A search function is provided to enable search on a selection of fields depending on the entity type (e.g. description, keywords, title and types for projects). This selection of fields used for the main search can also be changed through configuration. It is also possible to assign weights to each of those fields. To highlight the projects evaluated (and FAIRified) by FAIRplus, a highlight function is implemented (see below “FAIRplus results” for details).

OncoTrack

Data access link or link to access request form

Links to Project and Study views

“FAIRplus Evaluated” badge

Access Data

Export Metadata as DATS

Metadata download

Project

Project Title	OncoTrack
Project website	http://www.oncotrack.eu

Studies

Study title	OncoTrack
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General Dataset Information

Version	V1.0
Date of creation of the dataset	2017-01-05
Date of the last update of the dataset	2017-09-05
Data standards	CDISC
Experiment types	whole genome sequencing exome sequencing transcriptome array methylation array microRNA array RNASeq proteomics deep-Sequencing
Type of Samples Collected	Healthy Surrounding Tissue (near tumor) Blood Serum Plasma Tumor Tissue
Number of Samples Collected	>6000
Diseases in samples	carcinoma of the colon
Treatment of experiment	antineoplastic agent

Main metadata values. Fields in blue should be annotated with ontologies term

Figure 2. Illustration of the new Data Catalog user interface

¹⁴ <https://solr.apache.org>

¹⁵ <https://flask.palletsprojects.com/en/2.0.x/>

¹⁶ <https://jquery.com>

Bioschemas integration

In order to improve the findability of Data Catalog content through standard web searches, we integrated Bioschemas¹⁷ markup in all aspects of the Catalog. This markup, which is an extension of schema.org, is indexable by search engines and other services. Bioschemas is a flagship strategy of ELIXIR and is being widely adopted in life science resources, aiming to increase their FAIRness along the findability axis. The FAIRplus Cookbook includes recipes regarding search engine optimization using Bioschemas¹⁸.

In the first instance, we made use of the “DataCatalog” profile, which can be found on every page of the IMI Catalog, and the “DataSet” profile, which is built dynamically for each “DataSet” page from the human-readable content.

At present, there are no Bioschemas-specific profiles for “Project” and “Study” but we intend to work with the Bioschemas community to drive the creation of suitable profiles for these concepts by providing compelling use cases for both.

```

<script type="application/ld+json"> == $0
{
  "@context": "http://schema.org",
  "@id": "https://datacatalog.elixir-luxembourg.org/e/dataset/64f33e4f-0d6d-4062-86c5-9c3db4e3a99a",
  "@type": "Dataset",
  "dct:conformsTo": "https://bioschemas.org/profiles/Dataset/0.3-RELEASE-2019_06_14",
  "description": "OncoTrack",
  "identifier": [
    {
      "@id": "64f33e4f-0d6d-4062-86c5-9c3db4e3a99a",
      "@type": "PropertyValue"
    }
  ],
  "includedInDataCatalog": [
    {
      "@context": "http://schema.org",
      "@type": "DataCatalog",
      "name": "IMI Data Catalog",
      "url": "https://datacatalog.elixir-luxembourg.org"
    }
  ],
  "keywords": [
    "CDISC",
    "whole genome sequencing, exome sequencing, transcriptome array, methylation array, microRNA array, RNASeq, proteomics, deep-Sequencing",
    "Healthy Surrounding Tissue (near tumor), Blood, Serum, Plasma, Tumor Tissue",
    "carcinoma of the colon",
    "antineoplastic agent",
    "Oxaliplatin, Irinotecan, 5-FU, Cetuximab, AZD8931, AZD6244, Afatinib, Avastin, Regorafenib, Nintedanib, mTOR FR, BI836842 (IGF1/2 mAb), AZ1 (Tank-I), Volitinib",
    "RDA indicator v0.03",
    "Post-FAIRification assessment"
  ],
  "name": "OncoTrack",
  "license": "https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc-sa/4.0/",
  "url": "https://datacatalog.elixir-luxembourg.org/e/dataset/64f33e4f-0d6d-4062-86c5-9c3db4e3a99a",
  "distribution": {
    "@id": "https://owncloud.lcsb.uni.lu/apps/files/?dir=ONCOTRACK/sample_metadata_ETL/metadata_BSD_JSON&fileid=14712690",
    "@type": "DataDownload"
  },
  "version": "V1.0"
}
nl head script

```

Figure 3. An example of the page headers showing the Bioschemas integration for the OncoTrack dataset

FAIRplus results

All datasets FAIRified as part of the FAIRplus project are highlighted in the IMI Data Catalog through a “FAIRplus Evaluated” badge displayed in the general datasets list, search results and on the page for the dataset, as well as for the study and project associated with the dataset. On the dataset page, a dedicated tab summarises the outcome of the FAIR assessment with links to the full assessment and the data used to perform it (see fig. 4).

¹⁷ <https://bioschemas.org/>

¹⁸ <https://fairplus.github.io/the-fair-cookbook/content/recipes/findability/seo.html>

FAIRplus Evaluation ▼	
<i>FAIR indicators</i>	RDA indicator v0.03
<i>FAIR score, overall</i>	35.0%
<i>FAIR score, mandatory indicators</i>	46.0%
<i>FAIR score, recommended indicators</i>	13.0%
<i>FAIR assessment details</i>	Post-FAIRification assessment
<i>Dataset link</i>	OncoTrack public sample metadata, FAIRified v1

Figure 4. An example of a FAIRplus Evaluation result

DATS export and data download

We implemented export functionality that allows users to export all IMI Data Catalog data as JSON files conforming to the DATS data model. This facilitates the integration of the metadata with other metadata, as well as its import into other resources.

We also extended the “Request data access” option from the original Data Catalog to give users direct access to data in cases where no special data access permissions are required, e.g. for publicly available GEO datasets. For datasets with data access restrictions, we have improved the data access request functionality by streamlining the form. We have also implemented the first part of a login functionality that will eventually allow identified users to access content that they have already been approved for.

3.3. (Meta)data

We greatly expanded the content of the redeveloped IMI Data Catalog by including all public NCBI GEO datasets from the original eTRIKS Catalog as well as project information (Metadata within the “Project” component of the extended DATS model) for all approved IMI projects by parsing and curating selected content from the “Project Factsheets” of the IMI website¹⁹. In line with the new data model, we are now able to accommodate multiple datasets and studies for a given project.

There is an ongoing effort to further curate all the metadata in the Data Catalog, including adding ontology annotations where possible, for example for concepts such as disease, data type, sample type, sample source and experiment type. We also intend to actively engage with IMI projects for which currently only project-level metadata is available, to gather study and dataset-level information.

4. Discussion

The redevelopment of the IMI FAIR Data Catalog as part of the FAIRplus project, and in line with FAIR principles, has generated marked improvements across all aspects of FAIR.

Thanks to the incorporation of Bioschemas markup in the Catalog, the Catalog entries for

¹⁹ <https://www.imi.europa.eu/projects-results/project-factsheets>

most projects are now found on the first page of search results in Google, as well as returning top or even direct hits in Google Dataset Search. This improvement in **Findability** of project metadata is a great asset for any project that cannot submit data to public repositories for confidentiality reasons.

The streamlining of data access requests via the Data Catalog increases the **Accessibility** of project data for end users. Rather than having to navigate complex data access request systems, users will eventually be able to gain access to various types of datasets via the single point of entry in the Data Catalog.

By adopting the DATS model, an existing community standard that is interoperable with other standards such as DCAT and Bioschemas, we increased the **Interoperability** of Data Catalog metadata with other resources. Users are able to download DATS-compliant metadata and directly integrate it into any DATS-compliant resource.

Making all IMI projects discoverable in a centralised resource using a shared and curated data representation greatly increases the potential for data **Reuse**, despite the very diverse nature of the different projects. By carefully curating keywords for experiment types, data types and other concepts, and underpinning them with ontology annotations, users are able to discover otherwise unrelated projects or datasets that match a set of common parameters.

Finally, we increased the number of entries from 77 to 355, including a rise from 67 NCBI GEO datasets to 185, and increasing the number of IMI projects from 10 to 168.

5. Future Developments

As detailed in section 3.3, we have an ongoing curation effort to expand and improve the information presented in the IMI Data Catalog. We are also working on a data import pipeline to facilitate the inclusion of new information in the Data Catalog directly from a centralised, multi-purpose user submission system based at the UNILU. These curation efforts are done in cooperation with and supported by Elixir Luxembourg, ensuring the long-term sustainability of the metadata beyond the funding of the FAIRplus consortium and the IMI-JU.

The curation effort will also include improving the ontology annotations of the existing metadata. These annotations will in turn be leveraged by expanding the Catalog's search functionality to include semantic query expansion.

We are planning on making use of the inclusion of machine- and human-readable data use conditions to make it easier for users to request access to data for datasets featured in the Data Catalog. Machine-readable data use conditions, encoded in a standardised format using DUO²⁰ are a key component of FAIR data resources and facilitate the implementation of automatic decision trees to direct users to the correct data access route without the need for unnecessary human intervention.

We are also working on expanding our Bioschemas markup to cover the study and project aspects of the Data Catalog using appropriate markup profiles. The findability of scientific information is improved immeasurably through indexing in general-purpose search tools such as Google Dataset Search, DataCite and even the main Google search engine.

More generally, development efforts on the Data Catalog will continue to address emerging user needs and add new functionalities, with Elixir Luxembourg being committed to supporting the long-term sustainability of this invaluable resource.

²⁰ <https://github.com/EBISPOT/DUO>

6. Conclusion

The IMI Data Catalog has undergone a major redevelopment, including a new data model, new user interface and a number of new functionalities. While the main body of work is completed, we will continue to improve the resource in a number of ways, including adding new data, improving the quality of the existing annotations and providing more detailed information on data access procedures such as machine-readable encodings of access conditions.

The Data Catalog is a unique resource that cuts across data and experiment types and provides a standardised, curated representation of project- and data-level metadata for a diverse range of projects. It implements the FAIR principles in its design as well as improving the FAIRness of the metadata it presents. Continued development and curation will seek to further the status of the Data Catalog as a fully FAIR-compliant, mature resource of great value to the scientific community.

7. IMI Data Catalog Repository

All IMI Data Catalog code is available in a dedicated repository of the FAIRplus Github organisation, at <https://github.com/FAIRplus/imi-data-catalogue>. The repository includes full documentation on how to deploy a stand-alone version of the Data Catalog.

The IMI Data Catalog itself is available at <https://datacatalog.elixir-luxembourg.org/>.